

Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used in the treatment of male erectile dysfunction in the Prefectures of N'Zérékoré, Macenta and Beyla, Republic of Guinea

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Abstract

In the Prefectures of N'Zérékoré, Macenta and Beyla in southern Guinea, people make extensive use of medicinal plants to treat a number of diseases, including erectile dysfunction. The aim of the study was to identify the medicinal plants used to treat erectile dysfunction. Ethnobotanical surveys were carried out using questionnaires and individual interviews from 15 April to 20 May 2024 in the weekly markets of the urban districts of N'Zérékoré, Macenta and Beyla. The study identified a total of 31 plants species divided into 23 families used in the recipes used by traditional healers and herbalists to eradicate the disease. 28 recipes are prepared using these species. Species from the *Leguminosae*, *Zingiberaceae* and *Liliaceae* families are the most widely represented. Tubers, roots, leaves and bark are the most commonly used parts. Bark, roots, leaves and tubers are the most commonly used parts. Ces résultats constituent une base de données pour des études visant à évaluer le potentiel biologique et chimique de ces plantes.

Keywords: Medicinal plants; Ethnobotany; Erectile dysfunction; Traditional practitioners; Herbalists

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organisation, nearly 80% of the world's population relies on traditional medicine for primary health care [1].

Traditional medicine has a cultural value in Guinea and is present in all villages, where it is the first line of treatment for rural populations [2]. The widespread use of this medicine can be explained, on the one hand, by the fact that modern treatments using pharmaceutical products are very expensive and far beyond the purchasing power of the vast majority of the population. Secondly, the ineffectiveness and even side-effects of certain modern medicines justify this approach [3]. Numerous studies in Africa have identified a wide range of medicinal plants used to treat dysfunction [4-6].

Guinea, with its significant biological and cultural diversity, has a rich medicinal flora that contributes to the livelihood of rural populations. Despite ethnobotanical knowledge of medicinal plants, studies on plants used to treat erectile dysfunction are still in their infancy. The forest zone, one of Guinea's four (4) most culturally diverse natural regions, has a rich and varied flora that is still poorly understood. Many of the plants from this flora are used by the local population through traditional practitioners and herbalists to treat a number of illnesses, including erectile dysfunction. These medicinal plants, which contribute to the livelihoods of rural and urban populations, are significantly these plants are inventoried by communities, but little research has been carried out by botanists and other researchers. As a result, there is a real danger that knowledge of medicinal plants will be lost, given the pace of deforestation in Guinea, without

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their characteristics and biochemical composition being known. As a result, the study on the knowledge of plants used in the traditional treatment of erectile dysfunction in our study area is necessary and could contribute to the management of this disease but also lead to the development of a database.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sampling

With the support of the regional health inspectorate and the regional coordination of traditional practitioners in the administrative region of N'Zérékoré, the list and contacts of members of associations of traditional practitioners and herbalists were obtained. Only those with knowledge of the plants used in the treatment of erectile dysfunction and who had freely consented to be interviewed were included in the list. Interviewees were selected irrespective of age, gender, ethnicity or religion. Based on these criteria, 70 people were interviewed.

2.2. Ethnobotanical surveys

Ethnobotanical surveys were carried out among traditional medicine practitioners, especially traditional healers and herbalists, at medicinal plant sales markets in our areas of investigation. But first, the localities in which traditional medicine practitioners are recognised as having proven knowledge in the treatment of erectile dysfunction were identified. Contacts were therefore established with resource persons or local guides in the areas to be visited. The survey involved a sample of 70 people made up of traditional healers and herbalists. In each of the prefectures, we worked with traditional healers selected on the basis of their influence in their locality and the number of patients they received and treated. Meetings with traditional healers were always facilitated by a resource person from the area visited. Five markets were chosen on the basis of their importance in our study area, and in each of them we worked with six randomly selected women selling medicinal plants. The target localities were visited over a period of 40 days spread over two months (15 April to 25 May 2024). To ensure the quality of the data collected, the surveys were combined with the collection of botanical samples. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with traditional practitioners. Herbalists were visited at markets in the study area. The protocol for collecting samples is based on the purchase of plant recipes used in the treatment of erectile dysfunction, just like any sick person who comes to the herbalist for treatment. The botanical and ethnobotanical characteristics of the plants used, their use in single recipes or in combination, the organs used, the methods of preparation and administration and the dosage were noted, and all the specimens were collected. The vernacular names of the species were collected in the national languages (Kpèlè, Loma and Konianké). These various stages enabled herbarium samples to be taken and the species to be photographed. The plants obtained were identified at the Eco-botany Laboratory of the University of N'Zérékoré using the available flora.

2.3. Data processing

Microsoft Excel was used to process the data collected. It was used to enter the data collected, make calculations and construct histograms, diagrams and tables. The analyses focused mainly on the methods used to prepare the recipes and the contribution of each species (CPr), which makes it possible to assess the frequency of involvement of each species in the recipes. It was determined for each species using the formula: $CPr = (Nr/Nt) \times 100$ [7]. Where Nr: number of recipes involving the plant, Nt: total number of recipes.

3. Results and discussion

The ethnobotanical survey made it possible to interview 70 practitioners of traditional medicine, including herbalists and traditional practitioners (Table 1).

Table 1 Number of traditional practitioners and herbalists interviewed (n=70)

N°	Surveys	Head count	
		Men	Women
1	Traditional healers	33	6
2	Herbalists	29	2
Total		62	8

The table shows that there were 19 traditional practitioners, 9 of whom were women, and 7 herbalists, 1 of whom was a man.

3.1. List of plants used to treat male erectile dysfunction in the prefectures of N'Zérékoré, Macenta and Beyla

The ethnobotanical study in the three prefectures identified a total of 31 species belonging to 23 families (table 2).

Table 2 List of plants used to treat erectile dysfunction

N°	Scientific name	Family	Organs used
1	<i>Cassia sieberiana</i> (Johann Friedrich Gelin 1791)	Caesalpiniaceae	Root
2	<i>Picralima nitida</i> (T. Durand et H. Durand 1910)	Apocynaceae	Fruit
3	<i>Nauclea didderichii</i> (Ernest Henri Baillon 1887)	Rubiaceae	Bark
4	<i>Adansonia digitata</i> (Michel Adanson 1753)	Bombacaceae	Bark
5	<i>Milicia excelsa</i> (George Bentham 1849)	Moraceae	Root
6	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (Carl Peter Thunberg 1794)	Moraceae	Root
7	<i>Allium sativum</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Liliaceae	Root
8	<i>Allium cepa</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Liliaceae	Tubercule
9	<i>Daucus carota</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Apiaceae	Tubercule
10	<i>Zingiber officinal</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Zingiberaceae	Tuber
11	<i>Symphonia globulifera</i> (Jean baptise christophore, 1775)	Clusiaceae	Rhizomes
12	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1763)	Zingiberaceae	Trunk bark
13	<i>Xylopia aethiopica</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1759)	Annonaceae	Seeds
14	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Fabaceae	Fruit
15	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Asteraceae	Fruit, root, bark, leaf
16	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1763)	Arecaceae	Leaf
17	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Asteraceae	Bark and root
18	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> (Johann Muller, 1863)	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
19	<i>Funtumia elastica</i> (Ernest Baillon, 1884)	Apocynaceae	Whole plant
20	<i>Arachis pintois</i> (Krapovicas, 1994)	Fabaceae	Bark
21	<i>Citrus limon</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Rutaceae	Leaf
22	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i> (Robert brown, 1826)	Fabaceae	Root, Leaf
23	<i>Scorparia dulcis</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Scrophulariaceae	Trunk bark
24	<i>Bombax costatum</i> (Pellegrin, 1914)	Bombacaceae	Trunk bark
25	<i>Kalanchoe blossfeldiana</i> (Remon Hamet, 1934)	Crassulaceae	Trunk bark
26	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> (Ludwig Blum, 1826)	Euphorbiaceae	Bark.
27	<i>Pygeum africanum</i> (John Gilbert Baker, 1863)	Rosaceae	Tubercule
28	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (Thunberg, 1794)	Polygalaceae	Tubercule
29	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Euphorbiaceae	Tuber
30	<i>Garcinia kola</i> (Gustav Adolph Engler, 1895)	Clusiaceae	Rhizomes
31	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> (Linne, 1753)	Lamiaceae	Trunk bark

The survey revealed that of the 21 families, Euphorbiaceae was the most represented with 3 species, followed by Bombacaceae, Polygalaceae, Liliaceae, Zingiberaceae, Asteraceae and Moraceae.

Table 3 List of plants used against erectile dysfunction by locality and their vernacular names

N°	Family	Scientific name	Vernacular names		
			N'Zérékoré	Macenta	Beyla
			Kpèlè	Loma	Konianké
1	<i>Caesalpinaceae</i>	<i>Cassia sieberiana</i> (Johann Friedrich Gelin 1791)	Cassiawulu	Cassiawulii	Sidian (malinké)
2	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	<i>Picralima nitida</i> (T. Durand et H. Durand 1910)	Wolokpagaou	Golowolozè	Waro woroba
3	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	<i>Nauclea didderichii</i> (Ernest Henri Baillon 1887)	Yakounanwulu	Zié bazi	kounadjiri
4	<i>Bombacaceae</i>	<i>Adonsonia digitata</i> (Michel Adanson 1753)	Baranwulu	Cidaa wulii	Cidaa
5	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Milicia excelsa</i> (George Bentqm 1849)	Guéliwoulou	Kodawulii	Diaradjiri
6	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (Carl Peter Thunberg 1794)	Baliamou	Bilegulugui	Denbasidjiri
7	<i>Liliaceae</i>	<i>Allium sativum</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	L'ail gnagba	L'ail gnavhaye	L'aildiaba
8	<i>Liliaceae</i>	<i>Allium cepa</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Gnaba	Gnavhaye	Diaba
9	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Daucus carota</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Carote wulu	Carotegui	Carotii
10	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Zingiber officinal</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Lèmoukié	Zounhizègui	Gnamakoun
11	<i>Clusiaceae</i>	<i>Symphonia globulifera</i> (Jean baptise christophore, 1775)	Kékéné	Tègulu	Simbadjiri
12	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1763)	Kpoguien	Taakhizegui	Forotomèssè
13	<i>Annonaceae</i>	<i>Xylopiya aethiopica</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1759)	Hébbéwulu	Sèvègui	Touba
14	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> (Carl Von linne, 1753)	Minwulu	Milingulu	Tombi
15	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Gbagbatia	Glagol	Remèbassi
16	<i>Areaceae</i>	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i>	Towulu	Toowoului	Tindjiri

		(Carl Von Linne, 1763)			
17	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (Carl Von Linne ,1753)	Pélékpo	Guglugui	Palubasi
18	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> (Johann Muller, 1863)	Polonighan	Kpakpiligui	Bissanmèssè
19	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	<i>Funtumia elastica</i> (Ernest Baillon, 1884)	Héghéléwulu	Bolo Wôlôwologui	Kèedili
20	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Arachis pintois</i> (Krapovic, 1994)	Lowotihannaa	Tihangui	Singbilikedjoug bassibissan
21	<i>Rutaceae</i>	<i>Citrus limon</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Ganikpona	Nomolonkpodaye	lémounoukoumoun
22	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i> (Robert browr, 1826)	Simananwulu	Zooumangoulii	Néré
23	<i>Scrophilariaceae</i>	<i>Scorparia dulcis</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	Nalien	Magoei	Timitiminin
24	<i>Bombacaceae</i>	<i>Bombax costatum</i> (Pellegrin, 1914)	Wiyèlon	Guluiwalye	Boumou
25	<i>Crassulaceae</i>	<i>Kalanchoe blossfoldiana</i> (Remon Hamet, 1934)	Milanwulu	Dadaigui	Kalakissan
26	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> (Ludwig Blum, 1826)	Yakoliwulu	Kpesègului	Konkomananin
27	<i>Rosaceae</i>	<i>Pygeum africanum</i> (John Gilbert Baker, 1863)	Hinawulu	Djablongui	Safou
28	<i>Polygalaceae</i>	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (thinberg, 1794)	Lakoya	Mawalaye	Bali
29	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (Cqrl Von Linne, 1753)	Yakowulu	Gulu	Dembasindji
30	<i>Clusiaceae</i>	<i>Garcinia kola</i> (Gustav Adolph Engler, 1895)	Touwolopèlè	Touwiliwhanaye	Woromessèni
31	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> (Linne, 1753)	Kouwhulu	Koumigui	Zoungbran

This table shows that the herbalists and traditional practitioners surveyed belong to three language groups: Kpèlè, Loma and Konianké (table 3).

3.2. The various recipes prepared to treat erectile dysfunction

According to our surveys, 28 recipes are prepared from 31 plants (Table 4).

Table 4 Medicinal plants surveyed and how they are prepared

N°	Scientific name	Organs used	Method of preparation	Method of administration
R1	<i>Cassia sieberiana</i>	Root	Decoction	By mouth
R2	<i>Picralima nitida</i>	Fruit	Infusion	By mouth
R3	<i>Nauclea didderichii</i>	Bark	Cut up and put in a jug of water or white wine	By mouth
R4	<i>Adamsonia digitata</i>	Bark	Cut up, crush, put in a container and add water.	By mouth
R5	<i>Milicia excelsa</i> + <i>Securidaca longedunculata</i>	Root	The decoction of the roots will be mixed with honey and left to rest for two (2) days before use.	By mouth
R6	<i>Allium sativum</i> + <i>Allium cepa</i> + <i>Daucus carota</i> + <i>Zingiber officinal</i>	Tuber	Turn into powder and mix with honey	By mouth
R7	<i>Symphonia globulifera</i>	Tuber	Powder or kaolin to be taken in hot water; soup; white wine	By mouth
R8	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i> + <i>Xylopi aethiopica</i> + <i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Tuber	Powder + salt germ to be taken in soup; hot water	By mouth
R9	<i>Funtumia elastica</i>	Rhizomes	Decoction	By mouth
R10	<i>Arachis pintois</i>	Trunk bark	Crush leaves and prepare with meat soup	By mouth
R11	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Trunk bark	Put in a container add water and honey	By mouth
R12	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Seeds	Powder the bark and add water	By mouth
R13	<i>Scorparia dulcis</i>	Fruit	By decoction	By mouth
R14	<i>Bombax costatum</i>	Bark	Powder plus rock salt mix and put in porridge to consume	By mouth
R15	<i>Kalanchoe blossfeldiana</i>	Leaf	Decoction	By mouth
R16	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> + <i>Zingiber officinal</i>	Root +	Decoction + honey	By mouth
R17	<i>Pygeum africanum</i>	Leaf	Decoction	By mouth
R18	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i>	Trunk bark	Infusion	By mouth
R19	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Leaf	Powder + salt to be taken in hot water; juice or white wine or porridge	By mouth
R20	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Trunk bark	Powder + salt in hot water, juice or white wine	By mouth
R21	<i>Zingiber officinal</i> + <i>Xylopi aethiopica</i>	Bark.	Decoction + honey	By mouth
R22	<i>Funtumia elastica</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i>		Powder + salt	By mouth
R23	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i> +	Leaf + bark	Infusion from juice or white wine	By mouth

	<i>Xylopi aethiopica</i> + <i>Elaies guineensis</i> +			
R24	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Trunk bark + root	Powder + salt to be taken in hot water; juice or white wine	By mouth
R25	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i> + <i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Rhizomes	Powder to be taken in hot water; juice or white wine	Oral
R26	<i>Garcinia kola</i> + <i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> + <i>Bdens pilosa</i>	Leaf	Powder to be taken in porridge; broth; or white wine	Oral route
R27	<i>Garcinia kola</i> + <i>Adamsonia digitata</i>	Root	Powder + shea butter	Cutaneous (by massaging the penis)
R28	<i>Garcinia kola</i> + <i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> + <i>Bdens pilosa</i> + <i>Aframomum melegueta</i>	Whole plants	Powder + salt to be taken in the porridge; broth; or white wine	Oral route

R= recipe

The results of this table show that 28 recipes are prepared from 31 species. The most commonly used method of administration is oral. Only one recipe is administered by the cutaneous route (by massaging the penis).

3-3-Classification of plants by therapeutic potential

The contribution of each species (CPr) makes it possible to assess the frequency of involvement of this species in the recipes. It will be determined for each species by the formula: $CPr = (Nr/Nt) \times 100$, where Nr: number of recipes using the plant, Nt: total number of recipes (Table 5).

Table 5 List of plants used to treat erectile dysfunction and their contribution to recipe preparation (CPr)

9	Family	Scientific name	Number of recipes involving plants (Nr)	CPr
1	<i>Caesalpinaceae</i>	<i>Cassia sieberiana</i> (Johann Friedrich Gelin 1791)	1	2%
2	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	<i>Picalima nitida</i> (T.Durand et H. Durand 1910)	1	2%
3	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	<i>Nauclea didderichii</i> (Ernest Henri Baillon 1887)	1	2%
4	<i>Bombacaceae</i>	<i>Adonsonia digitata</i> (Michel Adanson 1753)	2	4%
5	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Melicia excelsa</i> (George Bentqm 1849)	1	2%
6	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (Carl Peter Thunberg 1794)	1	2%
7	<i>Polygalaceae</i>	<i>Allium sativum</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	1	2%
8	<i>Liliaceae</i>	<i>Allium cepa</i> (Carl Von Linne ,1753)	1	2%
9	<i>Liliaceae</i>	<i>Daucus carota</i> (Carl Von Linne ,1753)	1	2%

10	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Zingiber officinal</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	3	6%
11	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Symphonia globulifera</i> (Jean baptise christophore ,1775)	1	2%
12	<i>Clusiaceae</i>	<i>Aframomum melegueta</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1763)	8	16%
13	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Xylopia aethiopica</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1759)	3	6%
14	<i>Annonaceae</i>	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> (Carl Von linne, 1753)	1	2%
15	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> (CarlVon Linne ,1753)	4	8%
16	<i>Arecaceae</i>	<i>Elaeis guineensis</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1763)	1	2%
17	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (Carl Von Linne ,1753)	2	4%
18	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> (Johann Muller, 1863)	1	2%
19	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	<i>Funtumia elastica</i> (Ernest Baillon, 1884)	2	4%
20	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Arachis pintois</i> (Krapovicas, 1994)	1	2%
21	<i>Rutaceae</i>	<i>Citrus limon</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	1	2%
22	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i> (Robert browr, 1826)	1	2%
23	<i>Scrophilariaceae</i>	<i>Scorparia dulcis</i> (Carl Von Linne, 1753)	1	2%
24	<i>Bombacaceae</i>	<i>Bombax costatum</i> (Pellegrin, 1914)	1	2%
25	<i>Crassulaceae</i>	<i>Kalanchoe blossfoldiana</i> (Remon Hamet, 1934)	1	2%
26		<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> (Ludwig Blum, 1826)	1	2%
27	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Pygeum africanum</i> (John Gilbert Baker, 1863)	1	2%
28	<i>Rosaceae</i>	<i>Securidaca longedunculata</i> (thinberg, 1794)	1	2%
29	<i>Polygalaceae</i>	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> (Cqrl Von Linne, 1753)	1	2%
30	<i>Clusiaceae</i>	<i>Garcinia kola</i> (Gustav Adolph Engler, 1895)	3	6%
31	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> (Linne, 1753)	1	2%

Total			100%
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CPr: Contribution of each species; **Nr:** number of recipes using the plant; **Nt:** total number of recipes.

The table shows that *Aframomum melegueta*, cited 8 times, is used most in the preparation of recipes, i.e. **CPr**=16%, followed by *Bidens pilosa*, cited 4 times (8%). Species such as *Garcinia kola*, *Xylopiya aethiopica* and *Zingiber officinal*, each cited 3 times (6%), came third. *Funtumia elastica*, *Ageratum conyzoides* and *Adamsonia digitata* were each cited 2 times, with CPr corresponding to 4%. These species may be of interest in the treatment of erectile dysfunction. In these areas, herbalists have to contend with nature conservationists in the harvesting areas; a lack of supervisory structures; a lack of technical resources for harvesting, preparing recipes and preserving them; and limited access to credit to support their activities. Another constraint is the use of pesticides by people living in harvesting areas (rural areas), most of whom are farmers. This practice, which has become both an environmental and a social problem, is an obstacle to the future of this local medicine based essentially on plants and plant diversity in general.

4. Conclusion

Very little data is available on aphrodisiac plants in Guinea. The aim of this study is to contribute to the management of erectile dysfunction by providing the Guinean population and the scientific community with medicinal plants used in the treatment of male sexual disorders.

Plants have been used for a long time and knowledge of their therapeutic effects has been passed down from generation to generation.

Medicinal plants and traditional medicine play an important role in the health of people in many countries. They are of great importance to the people of Africa. They are a very reliable source for maintaining health, due to their geographical accessibility, lower financial cost and effectiveness in treating a large number of illnesses.

Our investigations led us to discover the recipes of several plants used to treat erectile dysfunction by healers and herbalists in the prefectures of N'Zérékoré, Macenta and Beyla. Thirty-one (31) plant species belonging to twenty-three (23) families are used in the treatment of IE. Species from the *Leguminosae*, *Zingiberaceae* and *Liliaceae* families are the most dominant. Bark, roots, leaves and tubers are the most commonly used parts. Infusion (44.44%) is the preparation method most used by the healers we met, followed by decoction (38.89%). Processing into powder is used on average. The oral route is the most commonly used method of administration. Only one recipe is used dermally by massaging the penis. Today, the practitioners of traditional medicine in our study area are facing difficulties linked to the lack of supervisory structures and technical resources for harvesting, preparing recipes and preserving them. Another constraint is the use of pesticides by people living in harvesting areas (rural areas), most of whom are farmers. This practice is both an environmental and a social problem, and constitutes an obstacle to the future of this medicine and plant biodiversity in general.

To ensure better preservation of the plant species used by traditional healers, we suggest that these practitioners be supervised; that training workshops be organised on the knowledge of plants as exhaustible natural resources, their importance, herbal techniques and the consequences of their abusive use throughout the country. The organisation of door-to-door awareness-raising days among healers and herbalists.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is to be disclosed

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